

Template assisted *para* C-H activation

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Synthetic organic chemistry has been revolutionized by transition metal mediated C-H activation in the last few decades. *Ortho* C-H activation has shown widespread growth in this regard primarily due in fact to the favourable 5-6 membered metallacycle required to direct the *ortho* C-H functionalization. Reaching out to the distal positions thus require special improvised techniques. In this regard, the use of directing group in reaching out to the *para* position has acquired a special place in the field of C-H activation in particular and synthetic organic chemistry in general. As such, the efficient use of such directing groups to reach out to the distal *para* position are listed in this review, thereby providing an alternative to withstanding general *para* electrophilic/nucleophilic reactions in synthetic organic chemistry.

Keywords: *Para*, directing group, metallacycle, C-H activation, transition metal.

Introduction

Transition metal mediated C-H activation has not only helped in modernizing the field of synthetic organic chemistry but also in remoulding the synthesis of natural products and pharmaceutical drug molecules¹. Vigorous research has been undertaken in developing various functionalizations at the sp² carbon of aromatic systems primarily due to the extensive presence of aromatic systems in the vast majority of these drug molecules. In this regard, *ortho* C-H functionalization has seen an widespread development by electronic factors or chelation assisted sp² C-H activation². This is guided by the much more favourable 5-6 membered metallacycle required to functionalize the *ortho* position. In stark contrast, reaching out to the *meta* and *para* positions required highly innovative and improvised techniques, primarily due to the angle strain involved in generating the larger membered metallacycle required to functionalize these positions. It took until the year 2012 to functionalize the *meta* position by C-H activation technique, when Yu and co-workers reported the *meta*-olefination reaction utilizing a nitrile based directing group³. Though *meta* functionalization has since gained widespread prominence, generating a directing group that can selectively functionalize the *para* position remained elusive.

Para centre just like *ortho* position are centres of high electron density and therefore prone to attack by electrophiles.

But a normal electrophilic reaction would result in the formation of regioisomeric mixtures of *ortho* and *para* products. The goal was therefore to obtain selectively *ortho* and *para* functionalized products. In this regard, there have been reports of selectively *ortho* functionalized products while preferential functionalization of *para* position have relied mainly on steric and electronic factors, thus suffering from poor selectivity and undesirable side products. Fascinated with this obstacle, Maiti and co-workers reported a highly efficient and effective template based approach to selectively obtain *para* functionalized products⁴. They overcame the long standing problem of reaching out to the farthest position of the aromatic moiety by introducing an effective and easy removable directing group and utilizing C-H activation strategy to obtain selectively functionalized *para* products. The importance of this *para*-functionalized products lay further in the novel and concise synthesis of natural products, pharmaceuticals and drug molecules. This review deals mainly with the directing groups that have been developed to selectively obtain *para* functionalized products. The main purpose of this review is to give a detailed overview of the various directing groups that have been developed to functionalize the *para* position with a high degree of stereoselectivity, along the way encouraging the scientific community to evolve the sparsely developed field into a notable beneficiary of the scientific community in general and chemists in particular.

Method development

For the past few decades, an enormous amount of attempts have been made to selectively functionalize the *para* position. Existing strategies relied mainly on steric and electronic factors and thus was limited to poor yields and regioselectivity. Those which overcame this problem required the use of an *ortho* chelating handle. Hence the main aim was to overcome the well-established problem of developing a strategy that will result in the formation of the selectively functionalized *para* products without compromising on the yields.

The challenge was overcome back in the year 2015, when Maiti and co-workers reported a template based strategy to reach out to the farthest *para* position. They developed a D-shaped template that was successful in generating highly selective *para* functionalized products of toluene moieties by utilizing a directing group C-H activation based approach (Scheme 1)⁴. The use of such a directing group strategy to obtain highly stereoselective *para* functionalized products had remained difficult to achieve till then primarily due to the formation of the highly unstable transition state while simultaneously activating the *para* C-H bond. The instability of the transition state could be attributed to the ring strain involved in generating the 16–17 membered metallacycle. Maiti and co-workers while generating the directing group further took additive measures in order to prevent the activation of the *ortho* or *meta* C-H bonds. As a result, the generation of the directing group was borne with some important concerns. Firstly, in order to activate the *para* C-H bond, the ring size of the metallacycle has to be larger than that involved in either of *ortho* or *meta* C-H activations. This would result in an associated rise in angle strain energy. Secondly, the coordinating group in the template must be large enough in order to be proximal to the *para* C-H bond without activating the *meta* or *ortho* C-H bonds resulting in a highly conformationally flexible assembly. The increased electrophilicity of the metal assures a ready C-X bond formation with the help of agostic

Scheme 1. D-shaped template.

interaction and which thus balances the huge amount of enthalpy rise caused by breaking the thermodynamically stable C-H bond.

A series of optimizations carried out by Maiti and co-workers led to biphenyl scaffold being the optimized scaffold, helping not only in providing the desired chain length but also introducing rigidity into the template skeleton, removing possibilities of *ortho* or *meta* C-H functionalizations (Scheme 2). The use of carbonyl and sulfonyl based tethers provided a hindrance to the selectivity of the result. After rigorous optimizations, diisopropyl substituted silyl centre provided with the optimum tether for the directing group. The silicon group was helpful in generating a larger silicon-carbon and silicon-oxygen bond distance. The sterically crowded isopropyl group played the most vital role in developing the directing group by inducing 'Thorpe-Ingold effect' and assuring closer proximity of the coordinating group to the *para* C-H bond by a 'steric-push'. As a result, *ortho* C-H activation was ruled out by the strain involved in the transition state while *meta* C-H activation was ruled out by the rigidity of the biphenyl system and the linearity of the nitrile donor.

Final scaffold

Ortho activation is disfavoured: highly strained scaffold

Meta activation is less favoured: rigidity of biphenyl and linearity of the coordinating group

Para activation is more favoured: longer chain length, flexible cyclophane like T.S., close proximity of donor to target C-H

Flexible 17-membered metallacycle in transition state

Scheme 2. Optimization of directing group for *para* functionalization.

The nitrile donor was initially considered to be at *meta* position with respect to toluene derivative but after careful optimization, the linearity of the nitrile donor was best affected when it is at *ortho* position with respect to toluene substituent and hence the final template forms a flexible 17

membered metallacycle in the transition state.

After developing the directing group, Maiti and co-workers tested *para* olefination on toluene derivative (Scheme 3). *Para* olefinated product was obtained in 71% yield with a selectivity ratio of 8:1. Control experiments resulted in a complete loss of *para* regioselectivity thus affirming the correct design of the directing group in functionalizing the *para* position selectively. The functionalization was extended to both electron ring and electron deficient arenes, as well as to a wide variety of olefins and bulky acrylates. Endocyclic double bonds were also consistent under the reaction conditions. This strategy was further appended with *para* acetoxylation of toluene derivative which proceeded with excellent yields and a high degree of selectivity (Scheme 4). The mechanistic cycle was proposed with the generation of an active pre catalyst obtained by chelation with the metal. This chelation in turn accelerated the C-H activation step. The macrocyclic metallacycle transition state was stabilized by coordination of alcohols with the metal catalyst (Fig. 1).

Scheme 3. Template assisted *para* olefination of toluene derivatives.

Scheme 4. Template assisted *para* acetoxylation of toluene derivatives.

Fig. 1. Mechanistic cycle for *para* olefination of toluene derivative.

This work was followed by *para* olefination of phenol derivative utilizing the same diisopropyl silyl based template⁵. This report on phenol derivative by Maiti and co-workers involved a simple switch in atom connectivity in the already developed template (Scheme 5).

As a result, this traceless directing group was able to generate *para* olefination of phenol derivative in 82% isolated yield with a 10:1 selectivity (Scheme 6). The reaction was inhibited in the absence of a heteroatom reinstating the importance of the heteroatom in the already developed template.

The creativity of this template based strategy in generating highly selective *para* functionalized products lay in the concise and efficient synthesis of many phenol based natu-

Scheme 5. Switch in atom connectivity in template assisted *para* functionalization.

Scheme 6. Template assisted *para* olefination of phenol derivative.

ral products and complex molecules. The synthesis of several other drug molecules were found to be competent under this template based strategy such as plicatin, drupanin and artemisinin (Scheme 7). The template could be cleaved *in situ* using TBAF to generate highly functionalized *para* phenols in good yields. Treatment with *p*-toluene sulfonic acid however generated silanol which could be used for another event of *para* functionalization.

An innovative iteration of template assisted *para* functionalization was put forward by Maiti and co-workers

Scheme 7. Late stage diversification of phenol derivative.

Scheme 8. Removal of cleavable auxiliary.

when they developed *para*-silylation of toluene derivatives using a second generation template (Scheme 9)⁶.

Scheme 9. Second generation template for *para*-silylation of toluene derivative.

The modification of the already developed directing group was essentially vital and a change in the coordination nature and strength of the template was required. After meticulous

optimization of directing group, the presence of electron ring methoxy substituent was found to be crucial in increasing the yield as well as selectivity of the *para*-silylated product. The authors reported an interesting observation in the H-bonding of the substrate and the solvent. Consequently solvent, HFIP played a key role in the reaction mechanism by H-bonding to the substrate and improving both the yield as well as the selectivity. Both experimental and computational insights into the role of the solvent were reported (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Mechanistic cycle depicting *para*-silylation of toluene derivative.

Thus the *para*-silylated product was obtained in a moderate yield and a high degree of selectivity (Scheme 10). The synthetic utility of this protocol was disclosed through late-stage modifications and by mimicking enzymatic transformations.

Not only using palladium as metal catalyst but template assisted *para* functionalization has also been carried out by using much cheaper ruthenium metal. The first report of Ru-catalyzed *para* functionalization can be traced back to the work of Frost in 2017⁷. Frost and co-workers utilized a *N*-phenylpyrimidine-2-amine based auxiliary which depicted a

Scheme 10. Template assisted *para*-silylation of toluene derivatives.

higher tendency to form *para* functionalized product over the *meta* one. The change in selectivity was attributed to the Ru-N coordination favouring *para*-selectivity compared to Ru-C coordination which favours *meta*-functionalized products (Fig. 3). The use of a base as reported played a crucial role in reaching out to the *para* position. While K_2CO_3 was essential in maintaining the coordination of ruthenium to nitrogen, KOAc was essentially required for ruthenium coordinating to carbon. Cross-over experiments between aniline and acetanilide essentially gave further forays in determining the coordination of metal to the heteroatom. Radical mechanism was supposed to be in play as depicted by the inhibition of the reaction on adding TEMPO. Further this strategy was well suited to quinazolines based anilines. The transformation was proposed to proceed through the formation of a four membered cycloruthenated intermediate through N-H activation of the directing group followed by a ruthenium promoted SET pathway. Radical addition *para*- to aniline nitrogen followed by rearomatization gives the *para*-C-H alkylated anilines.

Lan and Zhao group successively reported *para* difluoromethylation of ketoximes based template (Scheme 11)⁸. The strategy was well developed with a broad range of substrate scope and late stage modifications. The protocol

Fig. 3. Ruthenium catalyzed *para* functionalization.

proceeded through a radical mechanism similar to the one reported by Frost and co-workers. An interesting aspect of their finding lies in the weak interaction ability of the oxime which plays a key role in directing the selectivity from the *meta* to the *para* position, thus enabling the formation of the

Scheme 11. *Para* difluoromethylation of ketoximes.

para functionalized product.

Very recently, Zhao and co-workers reported *para*-difluoromethylation of anilides based directing group (Scheme 12)⁹. The synthetic novelty of this protocol lies in the generation of leflunomide and carprofen derivatives. Late stage diversifications were enabled while the reaction essentially went through a radical mechanism. Frost and Ackermann had reported *meta*-functionalization using phenyl pyridines based directing group¹⁰. However changing it to a pyrazole based directing group, completely regioselective *para* functionalized products were obtained. Perhaps the most interesting point from this strategy was observed when decreasing the electron density of the ring, the product selectivity tilted more towards the *meta* compared to the *para* product in pyrazole based substrates.

Scheme 12. Ruthenium catalyzed *para* difluoromethylation of anilide template.

Conclusions

The last few years have seen an unparalleled growth of one of the most important aspects of C-H activation. Many strategies were adopted in reaching out to the farthest point

of the aromatic core. Functionalizing the *para* position by installing the directing group followed by removable of it has led to the concise and efficient synthesis of a variety of natural product and drug molecules. Further, using this template based strategy has led to functionalization at the *para* position with excellent selectivity. In spite of this, many aspects still call for development to expand the scope of functionalization and introducing newer and better concepts to carry this protocol forward. A deeper insight into the mechanistic side and reaction conditions are required to be carried out in order to develop a full-proof strategy and obtain *para* functionalized products which could be used as precursors to generate a large number of complex molecules.

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